

A New Paradigm in Minor Oral Surgery Recovery, A 3D Approach with Trypsin, Bromelain, Rutoside & Diclofenac: A Randomized Double Blind Clinical Trial

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Abstract

Aim: This study evaluates the efficacy of a combination of Trypsin, Bromelain, Rutoside Trihydrate, and Diclofenac Sodium versus Diclofenac Sodium alone in managing pain, swelling, trismus, and quality of life (QOL) after minor oral surgery.

Materials and Methods: A randomized, double-blind, controlled trial included 60 patients undergoing minor oral surgery under local anesthesia. Patients were divided into three groups(20each):GroupA:Trypsin, Bromelain, Rutoside Trihydrate, and Diclofenac Sodium. Group B:DiclofenacSodium alone.Group C: Placebo.Medications were administered for five days. Pain, swelling, and trismus were assessed on postoperative days 1, 3, and 7, along with QOL measures evaluating the impact on daily activities.

Results:Group A showed greater reduction in pain and swelling on days 1, 3, and 7 compared to Group B. Trismus resolution and improved QOL were observed in Group A on days 3 and 7.

Conclusion:The combination of Trypsin, Bromelain, Rutoside Trihydrate, and Diclofenac Sodium effectively enhances postoperative recovery and QOL after minor oral surgery, outperforming Diclofenac Sodium alone in managing pain, swelling, and trismus.

Keywords: Pain, Swelling, Minor Oral Surgery, Trypsin, Bromelain, Rutoside Trihydrate, Diclofenac Sodium.

INTRODUCTION

Minor oral surgical procedure are most commonly performed procedure by oral and maxillofacial surgeons ¹ and is liable to produce certain unavoidable post operative complication as a result of post surgical inflammatory response, resulting in pain, swelling and trismus. These complications may have a significant effect on the patient's Quality of life.^{2,3} This pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage.^{4,5} In addition trismus and swelling are common postoperative sequelae which are related to local inflammatory reaction, with involvement of cyclooxygenase (COX) and prostaglandins activity ^{6,7} To reduce the side effects and increase patient satisfaction after minor oral surgery, it is important to facilitate proper management and prescribe medication such as corticosteroids,⁸ non steroidal anti- inflammatory drugs⁹ or a combination of corticosteroids, paracetamol and non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs^{10,11} or enzyme preparations such as serratiopeptidase.^{12,13} Many drugs are available to reduce inflammation and relieve pain. They act by interfering with the body's natural inflammatory response mechanisms; however their chronic use may lead to side effects. Over the past few years research suggested the role for more natural and safe alternatives for the management of pain and inflammation. Some areas of research include supplemental essential fatty acids, herbs such as ginger, turmeric, boswellia, proteases (Trypsin, Bromelain) and bioflavonoids (Rutoside). Common proteases include Bromelain from pineapple; Trypsin, Chymotrypsin from porcine (pig) or bovine (cow) origin. However, porcine sources yield higher specific activity than do bovine sources ¹⁴⁻¹⁹. Recent clinical studies have shown that Bromelain, Trypsin and Rutoside Trihydrate very potent and safe in relieving edema, inflammation and promoting wound healing. The anti-inflammatory effect of proteolytic

enzymes has been proved by several clinical studies and is considered to be a promising treatment for acute (e.g., sports) injuries, post-surgical and degenerative joint conditions.

The purpose of the present study is to evaluate the efficacy of this new drug combination containing Trypsin, Bromelain, Rutoside Trihydrate & diclofenac sodium versus Diclofenac sodium routinely prescribed for immediate management of Pain, Swelling, Trismus and overall Quality of life postoperatively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A randomized double blind case controlled trial was carried out in the Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College & Hospital, Nagpur. Total of 60 patients of both sexes were selected among patients who required minor oral surgery under local anesthesia (2% lignocaine with 1:80,000 adrenaline). Informed written consent was obtained from all participants. The study was approved by the institutional ethical and research committee. Patients selected had no preexisting medical conditions or were any on medications that would influence their ability to undergo surgery or alter their wound healing after surgery. The ethical number was obtained from ethical clearance committee-OS/2206/2020

INCLUSION CRITERIA: The inclusion criteria for the study were patients aged 18 years or older, those who provided informed written consent, and those requiring minor oral surgery under local anesthesia.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA: The exclusion criteria for the study included a history of compromised health status, allergy to the drugs used in the study, recent use of anti-inflammatory drugs or antibiotics, chronic use of any medication, and pregnancy or lactation.

STUDY VARIABLES

The patients were randomly distributed into 3 groups A- Trypsin 48mg, Bromelain 90mg, Rutoside Trihydrate 100mg, Diclofenac Sodium 50mg (FLAMAR 3D), Group B- Diclofenac Sodium 50mg and Group C- Placebo. Cap Amoxicillin 500mg was common all the every group. Every patient was given a packet of 25 tablets to be taken orally and continued for 5 days. The tablets were identical in shape. The study was a double-blind. The study medications were given by an independent surgeon to the patients; thus, neither the patients nor the operating surgeon were aware of the type of medication given to the patients. Rescue medication was given in the form of Tramadol 50mg.²⁰

The primary outcome variables were pain, swelling, trismus, and QOL scores recorded after surgery. Postoperative pain was evaluated using a visual analog scale, 10 cm in length, ranging from 0 for “no pain” to 10 for “the worse possible pain.” Swelling was recorded using scale from 0= none, 1= Intra-oral swelling, 2= Intra- and extra-oral swelling and 3= Obstruction of the angle of mandible. Trismus was measured by interincisal opening by Vernier calliper.

To measure the effect on QOL, a modified questionnaire was constructed to evaluate QOL after third molar extraction (Table I & II). It was translated into regional language and involved different items addressing Facial appearance, Social acceptance, Eating ability and speech.

They were instructed to answer the questions and rate on a 4-point scale Not At All (0) A Little (1) Quite A Lot (2) Very Much (3) their experience with third molar surgery. The total score range is 0 to 36. The questionnaire also included questions about the duration of effect on each element of QOL to be recorded

The other outcome variables were the demographic variables, including age, gender, and body mass index. The postoperative variables included the number of rescue analgesic tablets taken by the patients until day

RESULTS

The records of all patients from the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur. The mean patient age was 28.07 ± 6.14 years. No statistically significant differences were found in the age and gender among the study groups (Table 1). On day 1 the pain was almost equal in Group 1 and 2 (3.15 ± 0.81 and 3.15 ± 0.97 , respectively) and more in Group 3 (6.15 ± 0.67). In Group 1 and 3 pain decreased gradually at subsequent follow-ups whereas in Group 2 slight increase was seen at day 3 and then little reduction at day 7. Swelling was most severe on postoperative Day 3 and decreased gradually through the subsequent follow ups in all the groups with least scores in Group 1 and maximum scores in Group 3. Trismus was least on post-operatively on day 1 and again increased at subsequent visits in all the groups with again the best results in Group 1 followed by Group 2 and Group 3 at all the time of examination

When these differences were compared they were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) Table 3 shows that for facial appearance was least in group 1 (0.45 ± 0.51) followed by group 3 (2.45 ± 0.60) and maximum scores in group 2 (5.50 ± 8.86). Whereas for all the other variables of Quality of life (QoL) the least scores were seen in group 1 followed by group 2 and followed by group 3.

The differences for all the variables were found to be significant among the groups ($p < 0.05$). From **table 4** it was observed that the total patient score of the QoL scale had highly significant positive correlations ($P < 0.01$) with pain and swelling however negative correlations with trismus at all intervals.

DISCUSSION

The minor oral surgery can result in considerable pain, swelling, and discomfort. Swelling usually reaches its maximum within 48-72 hours of the surgical procedure.¹⁻³ Minimizing tissue damage can control the amount of postsurgical edema.⁹ According to Bonnefont et al, ice applied to the operated area decreases vascularity and thereby diminishes transudation. However, none of the study has verified this practice^{7,8}. The vasoactive amines cause vasodilation, thereby increasing blood flow to the inflamed area. The inflammatory process is necessary if healing is to occur but inflammation also causes edema, pain, and trismus. The Mechanism of action of these enzymes are taken up by the circulating enzyme inhibitors i.e. alpha antitrypsin and alpha 2 macroglobulin, level which rise steeply following injury and tissue destruction. This rise in inhibitor levels is responsible for the period of operative fibrinolytic shut down and maintenance of inflammatory edema which delay healing. These also facilitate the action of plasmin which is necessary to open up the blocked microcirculation, resolve oedema and initiate healing⁹.

TRYPSIN:

Trypsin is produced in the pancreas in the form of the inactive zymogen trypsinogen. When the pancreas is stimulated by cholecystokinin, it is then secreted into the duodenum via the pancreatic duct⁸. In the duodenum, the enzyme enteropeptidase activates it into trypsin by

proteolytic cleavage. Trypsin in the duodenum catalyses the hydrolysis of peptide bonds so that proteins can be broken down into smaller peptides⁹. Clinical studies exhibit that the anti-inflammatory effect of trypsin is possibly due to inhibitory action on the vascular permeability¹⁰ and its ability to inhibit the rise in C-reactive protein and enhance the rise in alpha 1-antitrypsin, alpha 2-macroglobulin¹¹. Trypsin-chymotrypsin has also been shown to modulate cytokine levels in burns⁴.

BROMELAIN

Bromelain is a crude extract from pineapple that contains, other components, various closely related proteinases, demonstrating, in vitro and in vivo, anti edematous, antiinflammatory, antithrombotic and fibrinolytic activities¹² Bromelain when applied topically as a cream (35% bromelain in a lipid base) is beneficial in the elimination of burn debris and in acceleration of healing¹³. Several groups have provided significant evidence for both the edema-protective and edema-reducing efficacy of Bromelain in various animal experiments¹⁴.. The analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects are reportedly due to inhibition of the arachidonic acid pathway of inflammation by selectively decreasing thromboxane generation, changing the ratio of thromboxane/prostacyclin (in favor of prostacyclin), and inhibiting PGE2 in addition to the direct effects on the nociceptors^{15,16}. Other reported anti-inflammatory mechanisms of action of Bromelain include inhibition of bradykinin at the site of inflammation via depletion of the plasma kallikrein system, and limiting the formation of fibrin by reduction of clotting cascade intermediates^{17,18}. A few clinical trials in patients with arthritis reported statistical equivalence of pain reduction, whether they were treated with Bromelain or Diclofenac¹⁹.

RUTOSIDE

Rutoside is a natural flavone derivative. It has anti-inflammatory, anti-allergy and immunomodulating activity. Rutoside inhibits platelet aggregation and decreases capillary permeability, improving circulation and acting as a blood thinner. It also strengthens capillaries and helps prevent venous edema in the legs, making it effective in managing venous edema and capillary fragility. As a powerful antioxidant, Rutoside neutralizes harmful free radicals like nitric oxide, which are released during inflammation. Its ability to lower MCP-1 levels both in vivo and in vitro contributes to its anti-inflammatory properties by reducing monocyte recruitment to inflamed areas. Additionally, Rutoside inhibits the phosphorylation and activation of Jun N-terminal kinase/stress-activated protein kinase, leading to the suppression of AP-1 activation and further modulating the inflammatory response.²⁰

COMBINATION OF TRYPSIN, RUTOSIDE TRIHYDRATE AND BROMELAIN

Combination of Trypsin, Rutoside and Bromelain has shown to have significant anti-inflammatory effects in several clinical studies. The use of enzymes like Trypsin, Chymotrypsin, Bromelain as anti-inflammatory agents came into practice after it was observed during 1950s in USA that parenteral Trypsin could be used to relieve post-surgical inflammation and that due to traumatic injury caused by sports²⁰ as well as inflammation due to conditions like rheumatoid arthritis, ulcerative colitis, and atypical viral pneumonia.

In a clinical study conducted in 2004, the efficacy of an enzyme-flavonoid mixture was compared with Diclofenac, a prescription NSAID. The proteolytic enzymes used were Bromelain and Trypsin. These three agents were used in the form of an enteric-coated tablet (to prevent the

enzymes from being destroyed by stomach acid) that contained 90 mg of Bromelain, 48 mg of Trypsin, and 100 mg of Rutoside. For the 6-week trial, the researchers recruited 103 middle-aged patients who had painful osteoarthritis of the knee with a disease flare in one knee joint. The results showed that Diclofenac and the Bromelain/Trypsin/Rutoside mixture were about equally effective in relieving the patients' pain and improving their mobility, with no serious adverse events in either case ²⁰.

CONCLUSION

We would recommend this new drug which give us the promising role in relieving inflammation and promote wound healing and might be a safer alternative in comparison to other drugs used for these conditions.

LIMITATIONS

Larger sample size is required for more generalization of the results of study . Also long term follow up is required for evaluating if the drug has any delayed side effects.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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		Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Total	p-value
Age (in years)		28.00 ± 6.18	28.00 ± 6.18	28.20 ± 6.38	28.07 ± 6.14	0.993*
Gender	Male	9	11	11	31	0.776†
	Female	11	9	9	29	

Table 1: Comparison of age and gender among the Groups

Table 2: Comparison of pain, swelling and Trismus at various time intervals among the Groups by one way ANOVA

Variables	Time interval	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Total		p-value
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Pain	Day 1	3.15	0.81	3.15	0.97	6.15	0.67	5.32	1.71	0.037*
	Day 3	2.75	0.44	4.95	0.50	5.60	0.82	4.65	1.48	0.021*
	Day 7	1.9	1.48	3.7	0.47	4.75	0.79	3.07	1.40	0.026*
Swelling	Day 1	1.35	0.51	2.57	0.44	2.75	0.44	2.52	0.85	0.034*
	Day 3	1.75	0.51	2.90	0.50	3.25	0.55	2.27	0.78	0.003*
	Day 7	0.70	0.47	1.70	0.57	1.70	0.94	1.37	0.71	0.028*
Trismus	Day 1	23.35	1.57	21.70	0.88	22.45	0.98	21.43	1.51	0.001*
	Day 3	20.15	1.74	24.80	1.63	30.20	0.77	26.12	3.29	0.025*
	Day 7	28.08	2.06	28.95	1.11	37.60	1.47	31.78	4.43	0.033*

*P<0.05; Significant

Table 3: Comparison of QoL subscales and total score among the groups by one way ANOVA

Variables	Group 1		Group 2		Group 3		Total		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Facial appearance	0.45	0.51	5.50	8.86	2.45	0.60	2.80	5.46	0.011*
Social acceptance	1.70	0.66	4.20	1.01	4.75	0.64	3.55	1.55	0.001*
Eating	5.40	0.68	12.25	2.53	11.85	1.60	9.83	3.61	0.001*
Speech	3.00	0.92	5.90	0.97	6.50	0.51	5.13	1.74	0.001*
Total QoL	10.55	1.50	27.85	10.19	25.55	1.73	21.32	9.75	0.001*

*P<0.05; Significant

Table 4: Spearman's correlation coefficient to assess correlation between the QoL subscales and objective parameters

		FACIAL APP	SOCIAL APP	EATING	SPEECH	TOTAL QOL
Pain	Day 1	0.255*	0.753**	0.776**	0.776**	0.689**
	Day 3	0.234	0.766**	0.748**	0.819**	0.676**
	Day 7	0.013	0.719**	0.548**	0.677**	0.445**
Swelling	Day 1	0.215	0.809**	0.737**	0.740**	0.654**
	Day 3	0.665**	0.679**	0.624**	0.632**	0.606**
	Day 7	0.254*	0.568**	0.544**	0.534**	0.530**
Trismus	Day 1	-0.260*	-0.423**	-0.434**	-0.389**	-0.443**
	Day 3	-0.215	-0.706**	-0.759**	-0.827**	-0.662**
	Day 7	-0.282*	-0.816**	-0.791**	-0.863**	-0.735**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Data presented as mean \pm standard deviation or numbers of patients.

*Analysis of variance.

† X^2 test.

QUESTIONNAIRE TABLE

		NOT AT ALL (0)	A LITTLE (1)	QUITE A LOT (2)	VERY MUCH (3)	TOTAL
A. <u>FACIAL APPERENCE</u> Have your noticed change in your look before & after Surgery?	Day 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Day 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Day 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
B. <u>SOCIAL ACCEPTENCE</u> Has your experienced change in your Social activity?	Day 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Day 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Day 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
C. <u>EATING</u> Have you able to chew/swallow food	Day 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Day 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Day 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
D. <u>SPEECH</u>	DAY 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	DAY 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	DAY 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	